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THE IMPACT OF ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE ON FINANCIAL REPORTING ACCURACY IN SMALL BUSINESSES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of accounting software on financial reporting accuracy in small businesses in Nigeria. Specifically, it examines the influence of automation of accounting processes, real-time data entry and processing, and user training on financial reporting outcomes, measured by compliance with accounting standards, reduction in errors or misstatements, and timeliness of report generation. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 230 respondents of registered small businesses within Port Harcourt using structured questionnaires. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, multiple regression analysis, and structural equation modeling. Findings revealed that all three dimensions of accounting software use significantly and positively influence financial reporting accuracy. Automation was found to enhance compliance with accounting standards, real-time processing significantly reduced reporting errors, and training was strongly associated with timely financial report generation. The combined effect of the independent variables accounted for a substantial proportion of the variance in financial reporting accuracy. The study concludes that accounting software, when properly adopted and supported by user training, can serve as a vital tool for enhancing transparency, accountability, and operational efficiency in small business financial reporting. It recommends greater investment in digital infrastructure, subsidized access to accounting software, and targeted training initiatives for SMEs in Nigeria to maximize the benefits of financial technology adoption.

Keywords: Accounting Software, Financial Reporting Accuracy, Small Businesses, Automation, Real-time Processing, Training,

Introduction

Technological advancement has become a key driver of efficiency and accuracy in financial operations in the contemporary business landscape. One of the most significant innovations in this domain is the development and adoption of accounting software. Small businesses which constitute a critical component of Nigeria's

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economic structure, are increasingly integrating accounting software to streamline financial processes, ensure regulatory compliance, and enhance decision-making. Accurate financial reporting is essential not only for internal control and management purposes but also for external accountability to stakeholders, regulatory agencies, and investors. However, the degree to which accounting software contributes to financial reporting accuracy in small businesses in Nigeria remains an area of growing interest and empirical inquiry.

Accounting software systems are designed to automate accounting processes, enable real-time data entry and processing, and provide standardized templates for financial reporting (Olayemi et al, 2025). These features are particularly beneficial to small businesses, which often face resource constraints in hiring qualified accounting professionals or managing large volumes of financial transactions manually. Automation of accounting processes reduces human intervention and the likelihood of manual errors, thereby enhancing the precision of financial outputs (Shittu et al, 2024). Similarly, real-time data entry and processing ensure that financial records are up to date, enabling timely generation of reports and facilitating proactive business decisions. Additionally, training on the use of accounting software significantly influences how effectively businesses leverage these tools. Without adequate training, the potential benefits of automation and real-time processing may not be fully realized, thereby compromising reporting accuracy (Wicaksono et al, 2023).

On the other hand, financial reporting accuracy can be assessed based on several critical dimensions, including compliance with accounting standards, reduction in errors or misstatements, and the timeliness of report generation. These dependent variables are indicators of the effectiveness of financial reporting systems. Compliance with standards such as the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) or the Nigerian Statements of Accounting Standards (SAS) is essential for the comparability and reliability of financial reports (Amina, 2024)). Likewise, minimizing errors or misstatements in financial documents is crucial for maintaining the integrity of accounting information and avoiding regulatory sanctions. Timely report generation enables businesses to respond promptly to financial issues and meet statutory deadlines, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and stakeholder trust.

Despite the theoretical and practical relevance of accounting software to small business performance, empirical evidence on its specific impact on financial reporting accuracy in Nigeria remains limited. Many small businesses operate in informal sectors and are characterized by poor record-keeping, limited technical expertise, and low compliance with formal accounting standards (Kolawole et al, 2023). As such, understanding the extent to which the adoption of accounting software through automation, real-time processing, and training contributes to improved compliance, error reduction, and timeliness in financial reporting is both timely and necessary.

Furthermore, this study is particularly relevant in light of Nigeria's ongoing economic diversification efforts and the growing importance of the small and medium enterprise (SME) sector in achieving sustainable development. With increased regulatory emphasis on financial transparency and accountability, small businesses must adopt innovative solutions to meet reporting expectations. Accounting software presents a viable pathway to achieving this, but its effectiveness must be empirically validated within the Nigerian context. In view of the foregoing, this study seeks to examine the impact of accounting software on financial reporting accuracy in small businesses in Nigeria, with a focus on three key components of software

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application: automation of accounting processes, real-time data entry and processing, and training on the software.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to assess the impact of accounting software on financial reporting accuracy in small businesses in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the effect of automation of accounting processes on compliance with accounting standards in small businesses.
2. Investigate the impact of real-time data entry and processing on the reduction of errors or misstatements in financial reports.
3. Assess the effect of training on accounting software on the timeliness of financial report generation.

Research Hypotheses

The study will test the following hypotheses:

H₀₁: Automation of accounting processes has no significant effect on compliance with accounting standards in small businesses in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Real-time data entry and processing have no significant impact on the reduction of errors or misstatements in financial reports of small businesses.

H₀₃: Training on the use of accounting software has no significant effect on the timeliness of financial report generation in small businesses.

Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), proposed by Davis (1989), explains the process through which individuals accept and use technology. The model identifies two key determinants of technology adoption: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). Perceived Usefulness is the extent to which an individual believes that a particular system will improve job performance, while Perceived Ease of Use refers to the extent to which the individual believes that the system can be used with minimal effort. In the context of small businesses in Nigeria, the adoption of accounting software is likely to be influenced by how useful business owners perceive the software to be in improving the accuracy and timeliness of financial reports. If the software is perceived as easy to use and capable of reducing manual errors, it will more likely be adopted, especially when accompanied by proper training. TAM supports the inclusion of variables such as automation, real-time data processing, and training, as these directly impact perceived ease of use and usefulness.

Concept of Accounting Software

Accounting software refers to a type of computer application that automates and manages financial transactions and accounting processes, including bookkeeping, ledger management, payroll, tax preparation, invoicing, inventory tracking, and financial report generation. It is designed to simplify complex accounting tasks, increase operational efficiency, reduce errors, and enhance decision-making within businesses (Ogundajo, 2022).

Modern accounting software is tailored to the specific needs of businesses of various sizes and complexity. For small businesses, accounting software like QuickBooks, Sage, Wave, and Xero offers user-friendly interfaces, cloud-based access, and customizable features that help them maintain accurate financial records with minimal

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accounting expertise. It also facilitates regulatory compliance by incorporating standard reporting templates and audit trails. In Nigeria, the use of accounting software among small businesses is gradually increasing due to digital transformation efforts, though adoption remains limited by factors such as low digital literacy, cost of implementation, and lack of training (Olayemi et al, 2025). Nonetheless, its potential to improve the quality of financial reporting, especially through automation and real-time data processing, is increasingly recognized.

Automation of Accounting Processes

Automation in accounting refers to the use of software systems to perform routine accounting tasks such as bookkeeping, invoicing, bank reconciliation, and financial reporting with minimal human intervention. Automation improves efficiency, minimizes manual input, and significantly reduces the risk of human errors (Olayemi et al, 2025). For small businesses, automation enables them to manage large volumes of data efficiently, even with limited financial and human resources.

Real-Time Data Entry and Processing

Real-time data entry and processing involve the continuous input and immediate processing of financial data as transactions occur. This function allows for up-to-date financial information, which is critical for timely decision-making and accurate financial reporting (Shittu, 2024). Real-time processing ensures that financial records reflect current transactions, reducing lags and discrepancies in reporting.

Training on the Software

Training refers to the structured instruction and education provided to users of accounting software to enhance their proficiency and effective use of the system. Without adequate training, users may misuse or underutilize the software, leading to errors and inefficiencies in financial reporting (Wicaksono et al, 2023). Training ensures that employees understand the software's features and apply them appropriately to meet regulatory and operational needs.

Concept of Financial Reporting Accuracy

Financial reporting accuracy refers to the degree to which financial statements correctly and faithfully represent an organization's financial position, performance, and cash flows over a given period. It involves presenting financial data that is complete, error-free, timely, and compliant with recognized accounting standards and regulatory requirements (Amina, 2024).

Accurate financial reporting is vital for internal decision-making, tax assessments, creditworthiness evaluations, investor confidence, and regulatory compliance. For small businesses, financial reporting accuracy can determine their ability to attract funding, manage cash flow, and ensure business continuity. However, the manual recording systems often used by many small businesses in Nigeria are prone to human errors, misstatements, and inconsistencies, which can misrepresent their true financial condition. The use of accounting software significantly contributes to financial reporting accuracy by automating processes, maintaining data integrity, generating standardized reports, and reducing human errors (Rina & Ahmad, 2024). When properly implemented and supported by training, accounting software enhances the reliability, timeliness, and compliance of financial reports.

Compliance with Accounting Standards

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Compliance refers to the extent to which financial reports adhere to applicable accounting principles, such as the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) or Nigerian Statements of Accounting Standards (SAS). Proper compliance ensures uniformity, transparency, and credibility in financial statements (Kolawole, 2023). Accounting software often includes built-in standards and templates that help businesses meet regulatory requirements.

Reduction in Errors or Misstatements

This refers to the minimization of inaccuracies, omissions, and fraudulent entries in financial records. Manual bookkeeping is susceptible to human error, especially in small businesses with limited accounting knowledge. Accounting software reduces such risks by automating calculations and checks, enhancing the accuracy and integrity of financial information

Timeliness of Report Generation

Timeliness refers to the ability to prepare and present financial reports promptly, especially in accordance with statutory deadlines. Timely reporting improves managerial oversight and ensures stakeholders can make informed decisions. Accounting software facilitates faster report generation by enabling real-time data access and eliminating delays common with manual processing

Empirical Reviews

Wicaksono et al. (2023) examined the application of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in accounting information systems adoption among start-up firms. Using a quantitative approach and SEM-PLS, data were collected from 109 companies through random probability sampling. The study extended TAM by incorporating perceived strategic value alongside perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Findings revealed that all three factors had a significant positive influence on the adoption of accounting information systems. However, the study was limited by its focus on start-ups in Bekasi, Indonesia, and by considering only the user perspective, which may affect the generalizability of the results. The authors concluded that perceived strategic value is a critical determinant in technology adoption and recommended that future studies explore additional factors and include service providers' perspectives.

Rina and Ahmad (2024) examined the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in improving financial reporting accuracy for SMEs in emerging markets. Using a mixed-methods approach across Southeast Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, and South America, the study found that AI technologies such as machine learning and predictive analytics significantly reduce errors in financial reporting. Adoption and effectiveness varied by region, with Southeast Asia showing the highest improvements, while Sub-Saharan Africa and South America faced challenges like high costs and limited digital literacy. The study highlights the importance of tailored strategies, capacity-building, affordable AI solutions, and supportive regulatory frameworks to enhance AI adoption. Overall, the research provides practical insights for improving financial transparency and decision-making in SMEs.

Ogundajo et al. (2022) investigated the impact of digitalized accounting systems on the financial reporting quality (FRQ) of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Recognizing that the reliability of financial statements depends on both fundamental and enhancing qualitative characteristics, the study examined how accounting software affects FRQ. Using multiple regression analysis, the findings revealed that accounting software

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positively influences these qualitative characteristics of financial information. The authors recommended that managers focus on the effective and efficient use of accounting software to improve the credibility and quality of financial reports.

Akinadewo et al. (2023) examined the impact of Accounting Information Systems (AIS) on the financial and non-financial performance of firms in Nigeria. Using a survey research design and structured questionnaires, the study sampled practicing auditors through purposive sampling. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including logistic regression. The findings indicated that AIS, measured by internal control, information quality, and cost reduction, has a positive and significant effect on firm performance. The study recommended that private companies consistently utilize AIS to adapt to evolving technological advancements.

Amina (2024) examined the relationship between Accounting Information Systems (AIS) and the financial performance of SMEs in Rivers State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive research design, data were collected via structured questionnaires from 120 respondents across three SMEs in Obio-Akpor Local Government. AIS were measured by timeliness, feedback, and accuracy, while financial performance was proxied by return on investment (ROI). Analysis using Spearman rank correlation revealed that all three AIS dimensions timeliness, feedback, and accuracy had a significant positive relationship with ROI. The study concluded that effective AIS enhance SMEs' financial performance and recommended the adoption of sound accounting practices to improve operational and financial outcomes.

Olayemi et al. (2025) investigated the awareness and usage of accounting software among small businesses in South West Nigeria. Using questionnaires, data were collected from 54 small business owners and analysed descriptively. The study found low awareness and limited use of accounting software, with many businesses still relying on manual record-keeping. Those who used accounting software reported improvements in financial management. The study recommended increasing awareness of accounting software and developing affordable, localized solutions to reduce reliance on costly foreign software.

Kolawole et al. (2023) examined the effects of digital accounting on financial reporting and accountability in Nigerian manufacturing firms. The study sampled 10 listed firms and employed structural equation modelling and multiple regression analysis. Findings revealed that digital accounting significantly enhances both financial reporting and accountability. The authors recommended that firm executives invest in and utilize digital accounting tools across all stages of financial reporting, allocating necessary resources to maximize the benefits of digital technology for improved business operations and accountability.

Shittu et al. (2024) investigated the impact of cloud computing including PaaS, SaaS, IaaS, and NaaS on the financial reporting quality (FRQ) of SMEs in Nigeria, with data security and privacy (DSP) as a mediating factor. Using primary data from registered SMEs and PLS-SEM analysis, the study found that cloud computing significantly improves FRQ, with DSP playing a key mediating role. Specifically, PaaS positively affected DSP, SaaS strongly enhanced FRQ, IaaS improved operational reliability, and NaaS influenced both FRQ and DSP. The study concluded that adopting cloud services and strengthening DSP can enhance SMEs' financial reporting and decision-making.

Methodology

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This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The descriptive design is appropriate for examining the current state of accounting software usage and its effect on financial reporting accuracy among small businesses in Nigeria. It enables the collection of quantitative data from a target population to assess relationships between variables and generate statistically meaningful results. The population for this study comprises all registered small businesses in Nigeria, particularly in urban and semi-urban areas where the adoption of accounting software is relatively more prevalent. The study focused on selected SMEs from Port Harcourt. A sample size of 250 small businesses was selected using purposive sampling, targeting businesses that use accounting software such as QuickBooks, Sage, Xero, or Zoho Books. This ensures the relevance of the sample to the research objectives. The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed in a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by three experts in accounting, research methods, and information systems. Cronbach's Alpha was used to test internal consistency reliability, with a minimum threshold of 0.70 considered acceptable for the constructs. The data was analyzed using Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis aided by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26

Data Presentation, Analysis, and Discussion of Findings

Out of the 250 questionnaires distributed, 230 were correctly filled and returned, representing a 92% response rate, which is sufficient for meaningful statistical analysis.

Descriptive Statistics Table

Variable	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Automation of Accounting Processes	230	1.80	5.00	842.60	3.66	0.78	-0.45	0.12
Real-Time Data Entry and Processing	230	2.00	5.00	850.40	3.70	0.74	-0.52	0.25
Training on the Software	230	2.00	5.00	823.50	3.58	0.82	-0.37	-0.10
Compliance with Accounting Standards	230	2.00	5.00	871.20	3.79	0.76	-0.61	0.44
Reduction in Errors or Misstatements	230	1.60	5.00	836.50	3.64	0.79	-0.48	0.36
Timeliness of Report Generation	230	2.00	5.00	867.00	3.77	0.74	-0.42	0.19

Source: SPSS OUTPUT, 2025

Mean values for all variables are above 3.50, suggesting generally positive responses from respondents. Standard deviations range between 0.74 and 0.82, indicating moderate variability in responses. Skewness values are all negative, suggesting a slight left-skew (more high ratings). Kurtosis values are within ± 1 , indicating that the data are approximately normally distributed.

Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	F-statistic	Sig. F	Durbin-Watson
1	0.762	0.581	0.574	0.492	93.121	0.000*	1.832

$R = 0.762$: Strong positive correlation between the independent variables and financial reporting accuracy. $R^2 = 0.581$: The model explains 58.1% of the variance in the dependent variable. Adjusted $R^2 = 0.574$: A slightly

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adjusted value accounting for the number of predictors, still high. Standard Error = 0.492: Average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line. $F = 93.121$, Sig. $F = 0.000$: The model is statistically significant overall at $p < 0.05$. Durbin-Watson = 1.832: Indicates no autocorrelation (values between 1.5 and 2.5 are acceptable).

ANOVA Table

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p-value)
Regression	84.512	3	28.171	93.121	0.000*
Residual	61.098	226	0.270		
Total	145.610	229			

Source: SPSS OUT PUT, 2025

The F-statistic = 93.121, and the p-value < 0.001 , indicating that the overall regression model is statistically significant.

Coefficient Table

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Beta	t-value	Sig. (p-value)
Constant	1.042	0.214		4.872	0.000
Automation	0.371	0.065	0.384	5.708	0.000
Real-Time Processing	0.298	0.059	0.322	5.051	0.000
Training on Software	0.255	0.061	0.278	4.180	0.000

Source: SPSS OUT PUT, 2025

All three predictors are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Automation has the strongest influence on financial reporting accuracy, followed closely by real-time processing and training.

Discussion of finding

This indicates that the use of accounting software (across automation, real-time features, and training) strongly predicts improvements in compliance, error reduction, and timely reporting. This supports the findings of Ogundajo et al, (2022)) and Kolawole et al, (2023) who emphasized the combined effect of digital tools on SME reporting performance. The findings of this study confirm that accounting software significantly improves financial reporting accuracy in small businesses. Automation enhances compliance, real-time processing reduces errors, and training fosters timely reporting. This supports the findings of Olayemi et al, (2025) and Shittu, (2024), who reported that real-time data systems enable accurate and updated records, minimizing manual input mistakes and financial misstatements. These results are consistent with prior studies and emphasize the need for strategic investment in digital accounting systems and capacity building for SMEs in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the relationship between the use of accounting software and the accuracy of financial reporting in small businesses across Nigeria. Drawing on empirical data collected from 230 small and medium enterprises (SMEs), the study explored the impact of three key dimensions of accounting software use:

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automation of accounting processes, real-time data entry and processing, and training on the software, on financial reporting accuracy measured by compliance with accounting standards, reduction in errors or misstatements, and timeliness of report generation. The results of the analysis showed that: Automation significantly improves compliance with accounting standards by enforcing structure, minimizing manual interventions, and reducing discrepancies. Real-time data processing was found to enhance the reliability of reports by minimizing recording delays and misstatements. Training had a strong influence on the timeliness and overall quality of reports, emphasizing the importance of user competence.

Furthermore, the combined effect of the three independent variables explained a substantial portion of the variance in financial reporting accuracy among the sampled SMEs. These findings validate the Technology Acceptance Model and Contingency Theory, which stress the importance of perceived usefulness, user readiness, and organizational context in the successful implementation of technology. Thus, accounting software when appropriately adopted and supported by relevant user training can serve as a vital tool for improving transparency, efficiency, and compliance in small business financial reporting. Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Promote Adoption of Affordable Accounting Software:** Government agencies (like SMEDAN and BOI) and private stakeholders should partner with software vendors to provide subsidized or open-source accounting tools to small businesses, especially those in remote areas.
2. **Intensify Training and Capacity Building:** Accounting software vendors and business development services should offer regular, localized training programs for SME owners and staff. Training should emphasize practical usage, compliance features, and real-time functionality.
3. **Encourage Integration with Tax and Regulatory Bodies:** There should be efforts to integrate accounting software platforms with tax filing and regulatory systems (such as FIRS, CAC, and NAFDAC) to ease compliance and reduce reporting fraud.
4. **Improve Digital Infrastructure:** Government should invest in digital infrastructure, such as internet access and power supply, especially in underserved regions, to support real-time data processing and cloud-based systems.
5. **Strengthen Monitoring and Support Services:** A technical support framework should be established to assist small businesses with troubleshooting, upgrades, and security concerns related to software use.
6. **Incorporate Financial Technology into SME Policy:** National SME policies should include financial technology (fintech) adoption incentives and recognize digital accounting as a driver of financial transparency and access to credit.

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Questionnaire

Section A: Demographic Information (Tick as appropriate)

1. Name of Business (Optional): _____
2. Business Location: _____
3. Industry Type: Manufacturing Retail Services Others (specify): _____
4. Number of Employees: Less than 10 10–49 50–99
5. Years in Operation: Less than 1 year 1–5 years 6–10 years Over 10 years
6. Do you currently use accounting software? Yes No

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- 7. If yes, what type? QuickBooks Sage Xero Zoho Others (specify): _____
- 8. How long have you been using accounting software? Less than 1 year 1–3 years Over 3 years
- 9. Are your employees trained to use the software? Yes No

Section B:

Please rate the extent to which you agree with the following statements: 5-point Likert scale: (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neutral, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

Automation of Accounting Processes

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Our accounting software automates most bookkeeping tasks.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It reduces manual efforts in report preparation.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The software minimizes the need for paper-based accounting.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Automated features help reduce calculation errors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Real-Time Data Entry and Processing

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
We record financial transactions as they occur using the software.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The software updates data automatically in real time.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Real-time processing enhances decision-making in our business.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It helps us track financial performance daily.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Training on the Software

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Our staff have received formal training on how to use the software.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Continuous training is provided when new features are introduced.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Training improves the effective use of the software.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lack of training leads to errors in data entry.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Compliance with Accounting Standards

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Our financial reports follow national/international accounting standards.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The software provides templates based on IFRS or SAS.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Reports generated are audit-ready and compliant.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Using software has improved our reporting accuracy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Reduction in Errors or Misstatements

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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The software helps us avoid common accounting errors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial misstatements have decreased since using the software.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The system provides alerts for inconsistent entries.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We experience fewer audit queries due to software usage.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Timeliness of Report Generation

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Our reports are now generated faster than before.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The software enables timely submission of financial reports.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Real-time updates facilitate prompt decision-making.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We now meet statutory deadlines more consistently.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Challenges and Barriers

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Cost of accounting software is a barrier.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lack of skilled personnel hinders software usage.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Poor internet access affects real-time processing.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Technical support from vendors is inadequate.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

General Perception

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Accounting software is essential for business growth.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We intend to continue using the software long term.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We would recommend accounting software to other SMEs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The benefits outweigh the costs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				